

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11176430>

TECHNOLOGY OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS BASED ON A COMPETENCE-BASED APPROACH

Ergasheva Barno Ziyavitdin qizi

Tashkent state pedagogical university named after Nizami, Teacher
ergashevabarno.uz@gmail.com

ANNOTATION

This article will talk about the competence of students of the Department of Pedagogy in the conditions of development. The content of pedagogical quality and professional training, which should be mastered for future educators, is covered.

Key words: *moderation, competence, intelligence, professional training, need, development.*

In the context of modernization of pedagogical education, modern requirements for the training of teachers are determined in the context of a competency-based approach and are reflected in the unity of the general cultural, professional and socio-ethical development of the teacher. According to experts, in order to become a professional, skilled educator in the future, not only through cognitive (knowledge) and operational-technological (skills, experience, practice), but also through its motivational, ethical, social and behavioral components. It is necessary to prepare future educators for professional activity. The competency-based approach is divided into two main concepts: competence and competence, competence - one of the main principles of person-centered education is the formation of life competencies in students along with knowledge, skills and competencies First of all, competence is derived from the Latin (competere), which means "to be worthy, worthy". Thus, competence refers to a person's knowledge, skills and experience, his or her actual suitability for a socially professional position, and his or her ability to perform tasks that are relevant to him or her.

Under the leadership of President Sh. Mirziyoyev, raising the quality and effectiveness of education to the level of modern requirements has become one of the priorities of state policy. The Commission for Critical Study of the Preschool Education System, approved by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 9, 2017 No. PP-3261 "On measures to radically improve the system of preschool education" a number of tasks have been assigned and all conditions have been created on the basis of state national programs [1].

Today, the rapid development of science, technology and industry requires the staff of the education system to raise the quality of education to a new level in terms of content, and every employee of the system, especially teachers, loads sulji functions. The main task of today's education system is to educate students to love their country, to rely on their knowledge and talents, and to learn independently using modern information and communication technologies. An effective lesson is based on the general training of the teacher, and the general training is based on the principle of continuous continuity. Based on the experience of the system in the development of state educational standards and curricula, draft state educational standards and curricula of continuing education in general education sciences based on a competency-based approach were prepared [2].

Knowledge of the skills and competencies that a teacher develops in his subject, the state requirements for him, the optimal ways and means to achieve this, as well as its basis, regulatory criteria will help the educational process. In this regard, it should be noted that the development of competencies of future educators in the learning process can be achieved not only through training, but also through the formation and implementation of educational tasks:

- Development of value-semantic attitude to the profession of educator;
- developing the need to create themselves as educators and individuals;
- to increase self-knowledge, self-education and activation of the process of self-creation as a future educator.

- The development of the creative potential of the individual, aimed at the self-development of the creator

individuality in teaching;

Our task was to combine direct and indirect, external and internal motivations in the process of organizing pedagogical lessons, which required the definition of specific tasks for the activities of teachers:

- Actualization of motivation of future educators for the development of self-esteem and personal responsibility, as qualities that determine their professional and personal development, self-development, self-education;

- Focus on creative education and professional activities related to the development of innovative projects aimed at improving the quality of modern education;

- Involvement of students in the creation of an environment that helps to realize their life skills, creativity in educational activities;

- Organization of joint activities and cooperation in various forms (business, role-playing games, discussions, competitions, creative design, problem solving).

- Organization of communication experience based on the values of civic and moral culture;

- Development of personal qualities and characteristics of the student as a person of professional significance

Thus, the process of learning based on the preparation of future educators for professional activity on the basis of a competency approach is the process of formation and development of an educator with continuous self-development and self-awareness potential - his abilities and in readiness; understanding the social significance of the future profession; encouragement of professional activity; setting tasks for teaching, educating and spiritual and moral development of the educator; use of modern methods and technologies to ensure the quality of the process, methods of diagnosing children's achievements; at the University of Pedagogy, such as defining and implementing an individual educational trajectory of their professional and personal development [3].

REFERENCES:

1. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 9, 2017 No PQ-3261 "On measures to radically improve the system of preschool education"
2. Ergasheva, B. (2022). TALABALARINING PEDAGOGIK MODERINIZATSIYA SHAROITIDA KASBIY TAYYORGARLIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 401-405.
3. Barno, E. (2023). O‘ZBEKISTONDA MAKTABGACHA TALIM MUASSASALARINING ZAMONAVIY TIZIMI. *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(3), 103-105.
4. Ergasheva, B., Maxmudova, D., & Ramozonova, B. (2023). TECHNOLOGIES OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY ON THE BASE OF A COMPETENT APPROACH. *MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH*, 2(10), 118–122.
5. Ergasheva Ba’rno Ziyavitdin qizi, & Qulbulova Rayhona Anvar qizi. (2023). MAMLAKATIMIZDA VA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARDA MAKTABGACHA TA’LIM TIZIMI . *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 10(4), 69–74.
6. MAKTABGACHA TA’LIMDA RIVOJLANUVCHI TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO‘LLASH USULLARI MD Akmalovna, BR Sadriddinovna, BEZ Qizi. *Science and innovation 2 (Special Issue 13)*, 538-540.
7. Ergasheva Ba’rno Ziyavitdin qizi, & Islomova Sabina Jamshidxon qizi. (2023). ZAMONAVIY TARBIYACHINING KASBIY KOMPETENLIGI. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 10(5), 60–62.
8. Ergasheva Barno Ziyavitdin qizi. (2022). KOMPETENSIYAVIY YONDASHUV ASOSIDA BO‘LAJAK TARBIYACHILARNI KASBIY FAOLIYATGA TAYYORLASH TEXNOLOGIYASI PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *QO‘QON UNIVERSITETI XABARNOMASI*, 5(5), 75–77.

9. Xasanova, S. (2022). ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ РАЗВИВАЮЩЕГО ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОСТРАНСТВА КАК ФАКТОР ГОТОВНОСТИ РЕБЕНКА К ШКОЛЕ. *Science and innovation*, 1(В8), 2199-2203.

10. Khasanova, S. (2021). THE ROLE OF HISTORICAL ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS IN THE FORMATION OF NATIONAL PRIDE BY PRESCHOOL ADULT CHILDREN. In *Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования* (pp. 103-107).

11. Khasanova, S. (2021). Formation of national pride in children through teaching description of historical monuments in Uzbekistan. *ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL*, 11(2), 734-738.

12. Sh.T.Xasanova. Tarixiy obidalar bolalarda milliy g'ururni shakllantirish vositasi sifatida. «Yosh olimlar axborotnomasi» – «Вестник молодых ученых» – «The bulletin of young scientists». №4(1) 2023.ISSN 2181-5186.